

On the Use of Embedded Graphite Patches for Cure in Resin Transfer Molding

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ABSTRACT

Resin Transfer Molding is a three step process consisting of preform preparation, preform infiltration and composite curing. The curing process can be prohibitively lengthy if the resin system is either slow curing or if the part has thick sections. The work presented here addresses the problem of reducing the final cure time by internal resistance heating of a carbon patch in the preform. This internal heating increases the internal temperature and promotes resin catalization. The implementation is described along with test results that show potential improvements in cycle times with this internal heating method for thick thermoset composites.

INTRODUCTION

Resin Transfer Molding is a three stage process which begins with the preform preparation and its placement into the closed mold. This is followed by the low-pressure injection of a thermoset resin into the fiber preform. The final stage involves curing the part which can be carried out by applying heat in an oven or autoclave. If the resin is a fast reacting system, then the part can actually be cured at room temperature. In general, the duration of the cure cycle varies depending on the part geometry and/or the resin system. For example, when the resin is slow-curing or the part has thick sections, the curing stage can become prohibitively lengthy and dominate the manufacturing time.

The work presented here addresses the problem of lengthy curing cycles when manufacturing thick epoxy/fiberglass composites. Initially, numerical simulations were performed by Albin [1] to predict the cure time of epoxy when fiber bundles were heated to various temperatures. The numerical simulations indicated that significant benefits to the cure cycle time were possible with internal fiber bundle heating. This research continues that investigation by developing a method for implementing and controlling resistance heating.

The proposed method applies a current through an embedded graphite patch. The low resistance of the carbon tends to raise the temperature of the patch. In this manner, the temperature of the composite increases from the interior toward the exterior. Furthermore, the localized resistance heating produces temperatures at the graphite surface which have the potential to catalyze the nearby resin. The subsequent heat generation along with the thermal conduction promotes curing of the remaining resin.

EXPERIMENTAL

MOLD DESIGN

A thick mold was developed to accommodate a 15 cm x 15 cm x 5 cm preform as shown in Fig. 1. Aluminum was chosen as the mold material due to its light weight, corrosion resistance, and workability. The mold itself consists of three separate segments that come together to form the final shape of the part. The middle segment makes up the depth of the final panel. The top and bottom segments are 1.27 cm thick aluminum plates with injection or overflow ports. The injection port is positioned in the bottom segment of the mold to facilitate injection of the catalyzed resin system from the bottom of the mold to the top. Experimental observations from Stabler, Tatterson, Sadler, and El-Shiekh [2] show that injection from the bottom of the mold will reduce void formation in the final composite panel. The overflow ports are positioned in the top segment of the mold at the opposite side from the injection port to facilitate the radial flow pattern of the resin. Two of the overflow ports are used to allow air to exit the mold as resin enters while the center overflow port facilitates the thermocouples and lead wires that are in the preform.

Figure 1. Aluminum mold used to produce thick parts.

MATERIALS

All of the experiments contained in this text were performed using, a bisphenol A type, Shell EPON 9405 resin and an amine type EPON 9470 curing agent. This resin was chosen due to its low room temperature viscosity and excellent mechanical properties. Anti-foaming agents BYK A 501 and BYK A 515 were added to the resin to decrease the chance of air entrapment in the resin prior to injection.

The fibers utilized in the following experiments included a random E-glass mat (PPG) and a random carbon mat. The E-glass made up a majority of the preform and final composite while the carbon mats were use exclusively as internal resistance heating elements in the panels.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fig. 2 shows the preform which consisted of either 26 mats, yielding a fiber volume fraction of 12%, or 44 mats, yielding a fiber volume fraction of 20%, of randomly oriented fiberglass with two sets of randomly oriented carbon fiber mats placed 1.25 cm from the top and bottom of the preform respectively. E-glass mats were cut from a large roll to 15 cm x 15 cm mats and stacked into the approximate shape of the mold cavity. Two sets of 9 cm x 11.5 cm carbon mats were then inserted into the stack of E-glass mats. Lead wires contacted the carbon mats along the edge measuring 9 cm which allowed current flow along the 11.5 cm length of the mat. The preform was compacted, heated by the carbon patches to soften the binder, and then cooled to yield a partially shaped preform. A trimming operation was then performed to complete the shaping of the preform prior to insertion into the mold cavity. Veil layers were placed on the top and bottom surfaces of the preform to give the final part a smooth surface finish.

Figure 2. Fiberglass preform with carbon heating mats.

Lead wires and thermocouple wires were inserted into the mold through the center overflow port and placed between the mats in the preform prior to injection. Thermocouples were placed above the bottom carbon mat, at the center of the panel, and above the top carbon mat to determine the temperature profile of the matrix during the curing process. The overflow port was vacuum sealed using OMEGABOND OB-101 room cure epoxy adhesive.

Prior to resin injection, a vacuum of 660 mm Hg (87%) was pulled on the preform, mixing head, and vacuum tank. The vacuum tank consisted of a 9.5 L closed cylinder with two vacuum ports in line with the overflow ports of the mold, a vacuum gage, and a vacuum pump connection. The benefits of vacuum assistance on the final void content of a resin transfer molded composite has been investigated by numerous research teams including Lundstrom and Gebart [3], Senibi, Klang, Sadler, and Avva [4], and Hayward and Harris [5].

Resin was injected into the mold at a pressure of 170 KPa until flow was detected at the two unsealed overflow ports. At this point the remaining vacuum was released and resin was injected into the mold until a steady stream of overflow was detected. The overflow ports were then sealed and resin was forced into the mold cavity until a pressure of 200 KPa was reached. The injection port was sealed at this point and final cure of the panel was initiated.

Cure of the panel was initiated by applying an AC voltage across both of the carbon mats. The voltage was selected according to a predetermined power requirement. Temperatures were recorded at a rate of 0.02 Hz while voltage was applied to the patch. The temperature readings were used to record thermal conduction from the patch and to identify the exothermic chemical reaction of the resin system during cure. In each case the composite was placed in the oven for a post cure at 120 °C to establish full cure and development of ultimate elevated temperature properties.

The final composite was tested for density, fiber and matrix volume fraction, and void fraction. Density measurements were taken using the ASTM standard water displacement method [6]. The density measurements were used to ensure a uniform composite. The volume fraction and void contents were also measured using ASTM standard test methods [7], [8]. Both volume fraction and void content were measured to aid in the mechanical characterizations of the composite.

RESULTS

CURE CYCLE PROFILES OF 12% VOLUME FRACTION PANELS

Fig. 3 illustrates a typical temperature vs. time plot for the thick fiberglass/epoxy panels that were produced in these experiments. The applied power for this panel was 11 Watts and the temperature displayed is taken from the center of the panel. The cure cycle is initially dominated by the conduction of heat from the carbon patches through the fiberglass/epoxy composite. Notice, the sudden temperature rise in the panel occurring at approximately 4 hrs. This sudden temperature rise is attributed to the exothermic reaction of the resin that takes place during cure of a thermoset epoxy resin. The peak temperature is attained at the conclusion of this exothermic reaction which is followed by conduction once again dominating the cure profile by releasing heat from the fiberglass/epoxy composite to the mold walls. This is characterized by the sudden decrease in temperature following the peak. The temperature eventually reaches a steady state some time after the exotherm is completed. Hence, all of the measured profiles have three characteristic features: the initial conduction of heat from the carbon patches through the fiberglass/epoxy panel, the exothermic chemical reaction in the resin, and the conduction of the heat from the exothermic reaction to bring the panel to steady state. However, each panel does have a set of distinct differences due to the power that is applied to the carbon patches.

Figure 3. Cure Cycle Profile for an Applied Power of 11 Watts.

Figure 4. illustrates the inverse relationship between the time to reach the peak temperature of the center of the composite and the peak temperature vs. applied power. In each case an increase in power coincides with an increase in peak temperature and a decrease in the time it takes to reach the peak temperature of the cure cycle. An increase in applied power also

coincides with an increase in final temperature in the panel. All of these variables can be directly controlled by the power that is drawn by the carbon patches placed in the preform. As the power drawn by the carbon patches is increased the temperature of the carbon patches is increased and the cure rate can be accelerated. For example, the time to reach the peak temperature for an applied power of 11 Watts is 6 hours while the time for the panel with an applied power of 14 Watts is 4.6 hours resulting in a 1.4 hour decrease in time to reach peak temperature with a 3 Watt power increase. Likewise, the peak temperature in the 11 Watt panel is 139 °C, which increases to 191 °C in the 14 Watt panel.

Figure 4. Relationship Between Peak Temperature, Time to Reach Peak Temperature, and Power in the 12% Fiber Volume Fraction Panels

CURE CYCLE PROFILES FOR 20% VOLUME FRACTION PANELS

The cure profiles of panels with a 20% fiber volume fraction exhibit similar cure cycle profiles when compared to the panels with fiber volume fractions of 12% including the initial conduction heating from the carbon mats through the fiberglass/epoxy composite, exothermic reaction of the resin system, and conduction cooling of the composite to steady state. The panels also exhibit the same increase in peak temperature, decrease in time to reach peak temperature, and increase in final temperature with an increase in power drawn by the patches.

Examining panels having an identical applied power of 11 Watts but dissimilar fiber volume fractions in Fig. 5, one will notice that the time to reach peak temperature in the 20% fiber volume fraction composite has been reduced from the time at the lower fiber volume fraction. However, peak temperature and final temperature change slightly at the same applied power. This can be attributed to the insulating capabilities of the fiberglass in the 20% fiber volume fraction composite which initially holds the heat emanating from the carbon mats inside the fiberglass/epoxy panel. By holding more heat inside the panel initially, the exothermic reaction of the resin begins earlier and the part reaches its peak temperature quicker in the 20% fiber volume fraction panels. For example, comparing the time to reach the maximum temperature of 135 °C in the 11 Watt applied power panels, one can see a change from 6 hours in the 12% fiber volume fraction panel to 3.9 hours in the 20% fiber volume fraction composite. This is a 2.1 hour reduction in time that slightly affects peak temperature and final temperature of the composite. This change in the cure cycle profile could prove to reduce the overall processing time of the panels with higher volume fiber fractions.

Figure 5. Cure cycle profiles for 20% fiber volume fraction and 12% fiber volume fraction Composites at 11 Watts.

When heating the panel from the outside in, as in an oven or autoclave curing cycle, the insulating effect of the fiberglass would effectively be reversed. The higher volume fraction composite would insulate the center of the panel from the externally applied heat and the exotherm would begin at a later time. Heat would be conducted to the center of a low volume fraction fiberglass/epoxy composite quicker due to the reduction in insulating fiberglass. Therefore, one would expect the cure cycle of a thick high volume fraction composite to be longer in an oven or autoclave curing cycle when compared to a thick lower volume fraction panel. This change in the cure cycle profile could prove to increase the overall processing time of a higher volume fraction thick section.

Table 1 represents data collected for seven thick fiberglass/epoxy composite panels. Notice, the trends in the maximum temperature, time to reach maximum temperature, and final temperature discussed previously. As the applied power increases maximum temperature increases, time to reach maximum temperature decreases, and final temperature increases. The significant reduction in time reach maximum temperature between the 20% and 12% fiber volume fraction composites with identical applied power is also shown in two cases.

The 10 Watt, 20% fiber volume fraction composite does not fit the overall trend. This particular panel was affected by the inability of the applied power, to initiate the exothermic reaction of the resin system. The absence of the exothermic reaction affected all three of characteristic regions identified in the cure cycle profile of this panel.

Fiber volume fraction and void contents are averaged values of six samples taken throughout the volume of the panel. The six void samples demonstrated a concentration of voids at the overflow side of the composite. This trend is also noted by Lundstrom and Gebart [3]. The voids also decreased in each case with an increase in fiber volume fraction. This trend is also illustrated by Kim, Hwang, and Lee [9].

Table 1. Characterization of Seven Thick Fiberglass/Epoxy Panels

Power (W)	Fiber Vol. Frac. (%)	Voids (%)	T _{max} (°C)	Time to T _{max} (hrs)	Final Temp. (°C)
10	12	0.33	135	6.4	86
10	20	0.19	98	8.0	95
11	12	0.26	139	6.0	90
11	20	0.14	131	3.9	96
14	12	0.26	191	4.6	120
14	20	0.22	192	2.2	130
16	12	0.35	203	2.2	157

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS

Results indicate that a graphite patch can be used as an embedded heating element in fiberglass/epoxy system. Internal heating is potentially advantageous when compared to external heating in thick fiberglass/epoxy composites. Peak temperature, time to reach peak temperature, and final temperature are all related to the power drawn by the carbon patch during internal resistance heating. Controlling these variables is critical to the success of this heating method. Further research is needed to correlate these power requirements to the optimum cure cycle for individual fiber/resin systems. The effects of internal heating on the mechanical properties of the system must also be examined.

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